

Investigation of Split TCSC on Kanpur - Ballabgarh Transmission System

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Abstract : This paper investigates the performance of the single TCSC and proposed split TCSC on transmission system where India's first TCSC project is installed in Kanpur - Ballabgarh (KB) line to ensure the fine tuning of line reactance by proposed split TCSC in place of existing KB TCSC. A three phase KB transmission system is developed in MATLAB/Simulink (SimPowerSystems) for a) without any compensation - b) with fixed capacitor (FC)- c) with FC + existing KB TCSC and - d) with FC + proposed split TCSC. The KB system is analyzed for a step variation of load and performance of the system is investigated with a closed loop reactance control method.

Keywords : single TCSC, split TCSC, TCSC reactance characteristic curve, power flow analysis, sensitivity analysis

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